

Creation and Performance of a Cognitive Summary Score in de novo Parkinson's Disease: Results from the PPMI Study

M. Brumm, R. Kurth, M. York, D. Weintraub ()

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Objective: To determine if a cognitive summary score (CSS) is sensitive in detecting early cognitive deficits in *de novo* Parkinson's disease (PD).

Background: Cognitive impairment is common in PD, even in *de novo* or early disease. However, the ability to track cognitive changes over time, including in clinical trials, is hampered by consensus over which neuropsychological tests to use, and how to utilize the results. An option that allows one to combine the richness and details of a neuropsychological battery with the simplicity of a single test score is to create a CSS after all detailed test results are normed on the same scale.

Method: Using baseline cognitive data from PD participants and healthy controls (HC) enrolled in the PPMI, the following steps were taken: (1) clean test score data; (2) determine which test scores to utilize for the CSS (6 scores across 5 tests assessing multiple cognitive domains); (3) transform standardized scores to z-scores; (4) create final HC and super healthy control (SHC) groups; (5) create regression-based internally-derived standardized scores from SHC group; and (6) create CSS by averaging all standardized test scores.

Results: Using raw scores, the PD group scored worse than the HC/SHC groups on nearly all tests (Table 1). Similarly, the PD scored worse than the HC/SHC groups, with a larger effect size for the SHC group, whether using published (Table 2) or internally-derived (Table 3) norms, with the biggest effect sizes for processing speed and verbal episodic memory. Using internally-derived norms generated similar results (Tables 2 and 3), with the additional effect of decreasing the standardized scores in both the PD and HC/SHC groups. Finally, the CSS had a larger effect size (PD vs. HC/SHC) than all individual tests except processing speed (Table 4).

Conclusion: PD patients perform worse cognitively than HC at disease diagnosis on all cognitive domains, most notably processing speed and verbal memory. Using a SHC group increased effect sizes, and using internally-derived norms lowers the scores of PD patients to "expected" levels. A SCC performed as good or better than all individual cognitive tests, and combines the richness of a detailed, multi-domain cognitive battery with the simplicity a single, equally-weighted score.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD subgroup	HC subgroup		p-values	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	SHC (N = 154)	PD vs. All HC	PD vs. SHC
Age at baseline, mean (SD)	63.1 (9.4)	61.2 (11.6)	59.1 (11.6)	0.0077	<.0001
Median (min, max)	63.6 (33.5, 84.9)	62.8 (30.4, 85.3)	60.5 (30.6, 85.3)		
Sex, n (%)					
Male	607 (65.8%)	154 (61.6%)	94 (61.0%)	0.2212	0.2548
Female	316 (34.2%)	96 (38.4%)	60 (39.0%)		
Education, mean (SD)	16.0 (3.1)	16.1 (3.1)	16.1 (3.0)	0.7029	0.8769
Median (min, max)	16 (5, 32)	16 (6, 24)	16 (8, 24)		
Missing	4	0	0		
Race, n (%)					
White	856 (93.3%)	221 (88.8%)	140 (91.5%)	0.0155	0.4051
Black or African American	18 (2.0%)	16 (6.4%)	8 (5.2%)		
Asian	14 (1.5%)	5 (2.0%)	2 (1.3%)		
Other	29 (3.2%)	7 (2.8%)	3 (2.0%)		
Missing	6	1	1		
Ethnicity (Hispanic or Latino), n (%)	32 (3.5%)	4 (1.6%)	2 (1.3%)	0.1288	0.1523
Missing	4	1	0		
Months since PD diagnosis, mean (SD)	8.5 (7.3)	N/A	N/A	—	—
Median (min, max)	5.9 (0.4, 42.8)	N/A	N/A		
Missing	5	250	154		
MDS-UPDRS Part III, mean (SD)	22.4 (9.7)	1.3 (2.1)	1.1 (1.8)	<.0001	<.0001
Median (min, max)	21 (3, 62)	0 (0, 13)	0 (0, 10)		
Missing	6	2	1		
MoCA, mean (SD)	26.9 (2.4)	28.0 (1.5)	28.3 (1.1)	<.0001	<.0001
Median (min, max)	27 (15, 30)	28 (20, 30)	28 (27, 30)		
Missing	8	0	0		
HVLT-R Delayed Recall, mean (SD)	8.3 (2.7)	9.2 (2.4)	9.7 (2.2)	<.0001	<.0001
Median (min, max)	9 (0, 12)	10 (2, 12)	10 (3, 12)		
Missing	7	0	0		
HVLT-R Immediate Recall, mean (SD)	24.3 (5.1)	25.8 (4.7)	27.0 (4.4)	<.0001	<.0001
Median (min, max)	24 (9, 36)	26 (13, 36)	27.5 (14, 36)		
Missing	7	0	0		
Judgment of Line Orientation, mean (SD)	12.8 (2.2)	13.1 (2.1)	13.3 (1.9)	0.0243	0.0079
Median (min, max)	13 (1, 15)	14 (2, 15)	14 (4, 15)		
Missing	10	2	1		
Letter Number Sequencing, mean (SD)	10.5 (2.7)	10.9 (2.7)	11.3 (2.8)	0.0607	0.0009
Median (min, max)	11 (2, 20)	11 (2, 20)	11 (2, 20)		
Missing	6	0	0		
Semantic Fluency (Animals), mean (SD)	21.2 (5.3)	21.9 (5.4)	22.6 (5.5)	0.0470	0.0018
Median (min, max)	21 (7, 41)	21.5 (10, 38)	22 (10, 38)		
Missing	6	0	0		
Symbol Digit Modalities Test, mean (SD)	41.9 (10.3)	47.3 (10.3)	48.8 (10.5)	<.0001	<.0001
Median (min, max)	42 (7, 82)	47 (20, 83)	48 (20, 83)		
Missing	9	0	0		

Table 1

Table 2. Published norms z-scores at baseline among de novo PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD subgroup	HC subgroup		Cohen's d *	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	SHC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs SHC
HVLT-R Delayed Recall, mean (SD)	-0.50 (1.18)	-0.10 (1.09)	0.06 (1.01)	-0.34	-0.48
Median (min, max)	-0.30 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.20 (-3.00, 1.40)	0.35 (-3.00, 1.40)		
Missing	6	0	0		
HVLT-R Immediate Recall, mean (SD)	-0.42 (1.09)	-0.12 (1.04)	0.08 (1.02)	-0.28	-0.47
Median (min, max)	-0.40 (-3.00, 2.40)	0.00 (-3.00, 2.40)	0.10 (-3.00, 2.40)		
Missing	7	0	0		
Judgment of Line Orientation, mean (SD)	0.65 (0.99)	0.83 (0.94)	0.89 (0.90)	-0.18	-0.25
Median (min, max)	0.80 (-2.81, 2.49)	0.95 (-2.21, 2.57)	1.03 (-2.21, 2.57)		
Missing	13	1	0		
Letter Number Sequencing, mean (SD)	0.52 (0.94)	0.61 (0.93)	0.71 (0.96)	-0.10	-0.20
Median (min, max)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)	0.67 (-2.67, 3.00)		
Missing	6	0	0		
Semantic Fluency (Animals), mean (SD)	0.10 (1.00)	0.17 (1.10)	0.25 (1.11)	-0.07	-0.14
Median (min, max)	0.10 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.10 (-2.80, 3.00)	0.20 (-2.60, 3.00)		
Missing	9	0	0		
Symbol Digit Modalities Test, mean (SD)	-0.40 (0.98)	0.08 (1.02)	0.19 (1.03)	-0.49	-0.60
Median (min, max)	-0.38 (-3.00, 3.00)	0.00 (-2.75, 2.90)	0.11 (-2.38, 2.90)		
Missing	12	0	0		

* Cohen's d was computed by dividing the mean difference between groups by the pooled standard deviation.

Table 2

Table 3. Internally-derived, regression-based z-scores at baseline among de novo PD and HC cohorts

Variable	PD subgroup	HC subgroup		Cohen's d *	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	SHC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs SHC
HVLT-R Delayed Recall, mean (SD)	-0.54 (1.14)	-0.17 (1.07)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.32	-0.48
Median (min, max)	-0.33 (-3.00, 1.56)	0.03 (-3.00, 1.61)	0.18 (-3.00, 1.61)		
Missing	7	0	0		
HVLT-R Immediate Recall, mean (SD)	-0.56 (1.11)	-0.25 (1.04)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.29	-0.52
Median (min, max)	-0.52 (-3.00, 2.21)	-0.18 (-3.00, 2.37)	0.06 (-2.88, 2.37)		
Missing	7	0	0		
Judgment of Line Orientation, mean (SD)	-0.24 (1.07)	-0.04 (1.01)	0.01 (0.95)	-0.18	-0.23
Median (min, max)	-0.03 (-3.00, 1.80)	0.18 (-3.00, 2.02)	0.19 (-3.00, 2.02)		
Missing	13	1	0		
Letter Number Sequencing, mean (SD)	-0.22 (0.95)	-0.12 (0.94)	0.00 (0.99)	-0.10	-0.22
Median (min, max)	-0.20 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.15 (-2.85, 3.00)	-0.10 (-2.85, 3.00)		
Missing	9	0	0		
Semantic Fluency (Animals), mean (SD)	-0.25 (0.96)	-0.12 (0.98)	0.00 (1.00)	-0.13	-0.26
Median (min, max)	-0.36 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.18 (-2.31, 2.73)	-0.12 (-2.31, 2.73)		
Missing	6	0	0		
Symbol Digit Modalities Test, mean (SD)	-0.56 (1.01)	-0.07 (0.98)	0.00 (0.98)	-0.49	-0.55
Median (min, max)	-0.56 (-3.00, 3.00)	-0.05 (-2.46, 3.00)	-0.04 (-2.46, 3.00)		
Missing	9	0	0		

* Cohen's d was computed by dividing the mean difference between groups by the pooled standard deviation.

Table 3

Table 4. Cognitive composite using published and internally-derived norms

Variable	PD subgroup	HC subgroup		Cohen's d *	
	All <i>de novo</i> PD (N = 923)	All HC (N = 250)	SHC (N = 154)	PD vs All HC	PD vs SHC
Published norms					
Composite (mean (SD))	-0.01 (0.64)	0.25 (0.61)	0.36 (0.61)	-0.42	-0.59
Median (min, max)	0.02 (-2.34, 1.99)	0.26 (-1.73, 1.99)	0.32 (-1.73, 1.99)		
Missing	17	1	0		
Internally-derived norms					
Composite (mean (SD))	-0.40 (0.68)	-0.12 (0.62)	0.00 (0.61)	-0.41	-0.60
Median (min, max)	-0.34 (-2.75, 1.76)	-0.12 (-1.85, 1.83)	-0.03 (-1.85, 1.83)		
Missing	17	1	0		

* Cohen's d was computed by dividing the mean difference between groups by the pooled standard deviation.

Table 4

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